

Estimation of Some Epidemiological Measures of Association in Multiple Comparative Trials

Soumik Banerjee* and Krishna Saha^{† ‡}

Abstract

Multiple comparative trials with binary outcomes are commonly used in biomedical research and other disciplines for estimating epidemiological measures by combining information from multiple comparative trials. The epidemiological measures are commonly estimated as a weighted average of summary statistics based on the 2×2 table data from each trial. Three of the most important epidemiological measures are frequently used: the risk ratio (RR), odds ratio (OR), and risk difference (RD). The RD/RR are preferable due to a more meaningful and interpretable treatment measure for binary outcome. The estimation procedures for estimating the overall RD/RR in multiple comparative trials with binary outcomes are very challenging and difficult, especially when the number of patients in a single trial is small and when the number of events is zero for some trials. Considering the above situations, we develop some efficient estimation procedures for estimating the overall RD/RR in multiple comparative trials with binary outcomes. We illustrate those estimation procedures by analyzing two real-life data sets obtained from multiple comparative trials in biomedical research.

Key Words: Clinical Trials, Binary Data, Likelihood Ratio Test, Risk Difference, Test of Homogeneity, Estimation.

1. Introduction

Multiple comparative trials with binary outcomes (see, for example, Beitler and Landis, 1985; Cooper et al., 1993; Chu et al., 2010) are commonly used in biomedical research and other disciplines for estimating the epidemiological measures by combining the information from multiple comparative trials. In multiple comparative trials with binary outcome, the epidemiological measures can be estimated as a weighted average of summary statistics based on the 2×2 table data from each trial. Three of the most important epidemiological measures are frequently used: the risk ratio, odds ratio, and risk difference. The risk ratio and odds ratio are both multiplicative measures of effect, whereas the risk difference is an absolute measure of effect.

The issue of deciding which effect measure to use in a particular application basically depends on how the study was designed. One would prefer to use the risk difference/ratio over the odds ratio due to a more meaningful and interpretable treatment measure for binary outcome. However, the estimation procedures for estimating the overall risk difference/ratio in multiple comparative trials with binary outcome are very challenging and difficult, especially when the number of patients in a single trial is small (see, for example, Cooper et al., 1993) and when the number of events is zero for some trials (see, for example, Beitler and Landis, 1985).

*Department of Quantitative Sciences, Canisius University, Science Hall, Buffalo, NY 14208, USA

[†]Department of Mathematical Sciences, Central Connecticut State University, 1615 Stanley Street, New Britain, CT 06050, USA

[‡]Correspondence

However, the estimation procedures for estimating the overall risk difference/ratio in multiple comparative trials with binary outcome are very challenging and difficult, especially when the number of patients in a single trial is small (see, for example, Cooper et al., 1993) and when the number of events is zero for some trials (see, for example, Beitler and Landis, 1985). For example, data presented by Cooper et al. (1993) from a Cancer and Leukemia Group B randomized trial clearly showed that the sample sizes for both treatment groups are very small ranging from 2 to 12 and data presented by Beitler and Landis (1985) also showed that for clinic 5 and clinic 6, the number of events for a control group is zero. Another important issue is that binary outcomes from the same clinic or hospital may not be independent, and estimating the overall risk difference/ratio without counting the correlation between binary outcomes within the hospital may often lead to misleading conclusions.

The choice of estimation methods for the odds ratio has been thoroughly studied and compared, but relatively little attention has been paid to developing efficient methods for the estimation of the risk difference/ratio. Taking into account all situations discussed above, we focus on developing estimation procedures for estimating the overall risk difference (RD) in multiple comparative trials with binary outcome.

In this proceeding, we have discussed various methods of estimating RD under null and alternative hypothesis (Guo, 2022) and also the procedures of testing the null hypothesis (equality of the RDs across multiple centers) developed in Banerjee et al. (2025). We provided the simulation results derived in Banerjee et al. (2025) and the application of the test procedures on two real life datasets. Subsequently, we have also discussed the estimation of RD using a couple of methods (Guo, 2022).

1.1 Basic notations and definition

Suppose, we wish to compare two treatments using the data combined for k centers. For each of k centers, we randomly assign patients to one of the two treatment groups.

Let $\pi_{ij}, i = 1, 2, \dots, k; j = 1, 2$ be the corresponding cell probabilities of the outcome of interest. Then, $\hat{\pi}_{ij} = X_{ij}/n_{ij}$ is the sample estimate of this probability, where X_{ij} and n_{ij} are the number of successes and the number of subjects in the i th center and the j th treatment group, respectively. The risk difference δ_i in the i th center is simply $\pi_{i1} - \pi_{i2}$. We are interested in testing

$$H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = \delta, \quad (1)$$

where δ is a true common risk difference between the new and the standard treatments.

2. Estimation Methods Under H_0

One simple meta-analysis approach is to assume a common RD across all studies, that is, the Common effect (CE) model, which is also commonly referred to as the Fixed effect (FE) model or equal-effect model. Let d_i be the observed risk difference for the i th center. The estimate of the risk difference for center i is

$$d_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2} = \frac{X_{i1}}{n_{i1}} - \frac{X_{i2}}{n_{i2}}. \quad (2)$$

Under H_0 , one can model for d_i as

$$d_i = \delta_{H_0} + \sigma_i \epsilon_i,$$

where δ_{H_0} is a common risk difference across all centers and ϵ_i is the random variation which can follow as $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, 1)$, and the σ_i describes the variation. Note that

$$\hat{\sigma}_i^2 = \widehat{var}(\epsilon_i) = \widehat{var}(d_i) = \frac{1}{n_{1i}^3} X_{1i}(n_{1i} - X_{1i}) + \frac{1}{n_{2i}^3} X_{2i}(n_{2i} - X_{2i}).$$

2.1 Weighted average method

The common risk difference δ_{H_0} can be estimated as a weighted average of individual risk difference d_i of each center, where the weight given to each center is the inverse of the variance of d_i as

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_0} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i} \text{ with } w_i = 1/\widehat{var}(d_i).$$

2.2 Mantel–Haenszel (MH) method

The weights based on the Mantel–Haenszel (MH) method which uses sample sizes to define weights as

$$w_i^* = \frac{n_{1i}n_{2i}}{n_{1i} + n_{2i}}.$$

Similarly, the common risk difference δ can be estimated based on the above weights as

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_0}^* = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^* d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^*} \text{ with } w_i^* = \frac{n_{1i}n_{2i}}{n_{1i} + n_{2i}}.$$

3. Estimation Methods Under H_a : Random Effect Model

If the null hypothesis is rejected, then the effects are different across centers due to their heterogeneous populations. To account for the heterogeneity of center-level true effects, the RE (random effect) model uses random effects to represent the between-center heterogeneity. Once rejecting H_0 , one needs to estimate the overall risk difference under H_a . Under H_a , one can model for d_i as

$$d_i = \delta_{H_a} + u_i + \epsilon_i,$$

where δ_{H_a} is the overall risk difference and ϵ_i is the random variation which can follow as $\epsilon_i \sim N(0, \sigma_i^2)$ and u_i is the random effect due to between-center heterogeneity which can follow as $u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2)$. The variance of the observed risk difference d_i is given by

$$var(d_i) = var(\epsilon_i) + var(u_i) = \sigma_i^2 + \sigma_u^2,$$

and the estimated variance of d_i is given by

$$\widehat{var}(d_i) = \hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_u^2,$$

where $\hat{\sigma}_i^2$ is the estimate of σ_i^2 discussed earlier and $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$ is estimate of σ_u^2 which will be discussed in section 3.

Once we obtain the estimated variance of d_i under H_a using the estimates of σ_i^2 and σ_u^2 , we can similarly obtain the overall risk difference δ_{H_a} , as a weighted average of individual risk difference d_i of each center, given by

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^{H_a} d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^{H_a}},$$

where $w_i^{H_a} = 1/(\hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_u^2)$ is the weight given to each center as the inverse of the variance of d_i under H_a .

3.1 Methods Under H_a : : Estimate of σ_u^2

The estimate of the between-center variance σ_u^2 can be obtained based on the following methods (Guo et al. 2022) discussed as follows:

- DL (DerSimonian and Laird, 1986) estimator
- HO (Hedges and Olkin, 1985) estimator
- PM (Paule and Mandel, 1982) estimator
- ML (Maximum Likelihood) estimator
- Restricted ML estimator
- HS (Hunter and Schmidt, 2015) estimator
- SJ (Sidik-Jonkman (2005)) estimator
- EB (Empirical Bayes) estimator

DL Estimator: The DL estimator is the most widely used method to estimate σ_u^2 in the current literature. The estimator is given by: $\hat{\sigma}_{u,DL}^2 =$

$$\begin{cases} [Q - (k - 1)] / [\sum_i^k w_i - \frac{\sum_i^k w_i^2}{\sum_i^k w_i}], & Q > k - 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where $Q = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0})^2$ with $w_i = 1/\widehat{var}(d_i)$ is the Cochran's Q heterogeneity statistic, k is the number of studies included in the meta-analysis.

HO Estimator: The HO estimator is an unbiased estimator of σ_u^2 given by;

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u,HE}^2 = \frac{\sum_i^k (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0})^2}{k - 1} - \frac{1}{k} \sum_i^k \hat{\sigma}_i^2.$$

PM Estimator: The PM estimator applies iterations to the generalized Q statistic.

$$Q_{PM}^{(r+1)} = \sum_i^k w_{i,PM}^{(r)} (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{PM}^{(r)}), \hat{\delta}_{PM}^{(r)} = \frac{\sum_i^k w_{i,PM}^{(r)} d_i}{\sum_i^k w_{i,PM}^{(r)}}, w_{i,PM}^{(r)} = (\hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{PM}^{2,(r)})^{-1}$$

The generalized Q statistic is expected to equal $k - 1$, and $Q_{PM}^{(r+1)}$ is the generalized Q statistic at the $(r + 1)$ th iteration. The $\hat{\delta}_{PM}^{(r)}$ and $\hat{\sigma}_{PM}^{2,(r)}$ are the estimates of $\delta_{PM}^{(r)}$ and $\sigma_{PM}^{2,(r)}$ at the r 'th iteration.

ML Estimator: The RE model is essentially a linear mixed model, which could be implemented by the ML estimation. The logarithmic likelihood function given by:

$$\log L(\delta_{ML}, \sigma_{ML}^2 | d_1, d_2, \dots, d_k) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^k \log(\sigma_{ML}^2 + \sigma_i^2) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(d_i - \delta_{ML})^2}{\sigma_{ML}^2 + \sigma_i^2}$$

Taking partial derivatives to the log-likelihood function, δ_{ML}^2 , could be solved via the following equation:

$$\hat{\delta}_{ML}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{i,ML}^2 [(d_i - \hat{\delta}_{ML})^2 - \hat{\sigma}_i^2]}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{i,ML}^2}$$

where $w_{i,ML} = (\hat{\delta}_{ML}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_i^2)^{-1}$ and $\hat{\delta}_{ML}$ is the estimated δ_{ML} . We estimate $\hat{\sigma}_{ML}$ and δ_{ML} through iterations.

Restricted ML estimator: The ML estimator fails to account for the heterogeneity of the data and also, is sometimes negatively biased; the Restricted ML estimator (REML) solves these problems by a transformation. Specifically, the REML estimation modifies the log-likelihood function as

$$\log L(\sigma_{REML}^2 | d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_k) = -\frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^k \log(\sigma_{REML}^2 + \sigma_i^2) + \log \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{1}{\sigma_{REML}^2 + \sigma_i^2} + \frac{1}{w_{i,REML}} \right]$$

where $\hat{\delta}_{ML}$ is the likelihood-based estimate of δ , which is identical to the obtained as the ML estimator. The weight $w_{i,REML}$ is $(\hat{\sigma}_{REML}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_i^2)^{-1}$. The estimation also requires iterations.

HS Estimator: The HS estimator is an unbiased estimate of σ_u^2 , which is given by,

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u,HS}^2 = \frac{\sum_i^k w_i (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0})^2}{\sum_i^k w_i} - \frac{\sum_i^k w_i \hat{\sigma}_i^2}{\sum_i^k w_i}$$

SJ Estimator: The SJ estimator is a general between-study variance estimator that is based on the weighted residual sum of squares as follows:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{SJ}^2 = \frac{1}{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{(d_i - \hat{\delta}_{\hat{v}})^2}{\hat{v}_{i,SJ}}$$

Here $\delta_{\hat{v}} = \sum_{i=1}^k \hat{v}_{i,SJ}^{-1} d_i / \sum_{i=1}^k \hat{v}_{i,SJ}^{-1}$, $\hat{v}_{i,SJ} = \hat{r}_{i,SJ} + 1$, and $\hat{r}_{i,SJ} = \hat{\sigma}_i^2 / \hat{\sigma}_0^2$, where $\hat{\sigma}_0$ is a rough estimate of τ such that $\hat{\sigma}_0^2 = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (d_i - \hat{d})^2$ with $\hat{d} = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k d_i$.

EB estimator: The EB estimator is a multi-parameter shrinkage estimator of σ_u . If δ_k is the true effect size for study k and $\hat{\delta}_{H_0}$ is the effect estimate from the weighted average method, then

$$d_i | \delta_k \sim N(\delta_k, \sigma_i^2), \delta_k | \hat{\delta}_{H_0}, \sigma_{EB}^2 \sim N(\hat{\delta}_{H_0}, \sigma_{EB}^2), i = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

The posterior distribution of δ_i is:

$$\delta_i | d_i, \hat{\delta}_{H_0}, \sigma_{EB}^2 \sim N(\delta_i^*, \sigma_i^2 (1 - B_i))$$

where $\delta_i^* = (1 - B_i)d_i + B_i \hat{\delta}_{H_0}$ and $B_i = \sigma_i^2 / (\sigma_i^2 + \sigma_{EB}^2)$. Similar to $\hat{\sigma}_{REML}^2$, $\hat{\sigma}_{EB}^2$ can be estimated by iterations using the following equations if the within-study variances σ_i^2 are homogeneous;

$$\hat{\sigma}_{EB}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{i,EB} [\frac{k}{k-1} (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0}) - \hat{\sigma}_i^2]}{\sum_{i=1}^k W_{i,EB}} \text{ where } w_{i,EB} = (\hat{\tau}_{EB}^2 + \hat{\sigma}_i^2)^{-1}.$$

4. Test Procedures for testing the homogeneity of risk difference

The test procedures for testing $H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_K = \delta$ proposed by Lipsitz et al. (1998) and also developed by Banerjee et al. (2025) are discussed briefly as follows:

4.1 Non-parametric test procedures

Let $d_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$, where the cell probabilities $\hat{\pi}_{ij} = X_{ij}/n_{ij}$ and X_{ij}^s are assumed to follow binomial distribution with $X_{ij} \sim \text{Bin}(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij})$, $i = 1, \dots, k$ and $j = 1, 2$.

Then, $\hat{\delta} = \sum(d_i/\hat{w}_i) / \sum(1/\hat{w}_i)$ where $\hat{w}_i = \widehat{\text{Var}}(d_i) = (\hat{\pi}_{i1}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i1})/(n_{i1} - 1) + (\hat{\pi}_{i2}(1 - \hat{\pi}_{i2}))/(n_{i2} - 1))$.

As all $n_{ij} \rightarrow \infty$, the weighted least squares test statistic

$$Q_{WLS} = \sum (d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 / \hat{w}_i \sim \chi_{k'-1}^2,$$

where $k' = k - q$ with q being the number of centers in which $\hat{w}_i = 0$.

As all $k \rightarrow \infty$, they proposed the test statistic

$$Z_{WLS}^2 = (Q_{WLS} - (k' - 1))^2 / [2(k' - 1)] \sim F_{1, (k'-1)}.$$

To improve the normal approximation of a chi-square distribution of Q_{WLS} , Lui and Kelly (2000) proposed the following test statistic as

$$Z_{LWLS} = \frac{\ln[Q_{WLS}/(k' - 1)]/2 + 1/[2(k' - 1)]}{\sqrt{1/[2(k' - 1)]}} \sim N(0, 1)$$

When all n_{ij} 's are not large enough, the performances of Q_{WLS} and Z_{WLS}^2 are expected not to be satisfactory. To improve this, Lipsitz et al. (1998) proposed the following three weighted test statistics as follows:

$$Z_{WLS,R}^2 = (Q_{WLS} - k')^2 / \sum [(d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 / \hat{w}_i - 1]^2$$

$$Z_V^2 = [\sum ((d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 - \hat{w}_i) / a_i]^2 / \sum [(d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 - \hat{w}_i]^2 / a_i^2$$

$$Z_K^2 = [\sum ((d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 - \hat{w}_i) / ((1/n_{i1}) + (1/n_{i2}))]^2 / \sum [(d_i - \hat{\delta})^2 - \hat{w}_i]^2 / ((1/n_{i1}) + (1/n_{i2}))^4$$

4.2 Parametric test procedures

Due to the heavy dependence on the number of clusters and the average sample size, Banerjee et al. (2025) developed two model based (parametric) test procedures.

Binomial Likelihood ratio test (LRT)

Assume $X_{ij} \sim \text{Bin}(n_{ij}, \pi_{ij})$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$; $j = 1, 2$. Then the log-likelihood can be written as

$$\ln L = \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1} + \sum_i x_{i2} \ln \pi_{i2} + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln(1 - \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln(1 - \pi_{i2})$$

Recall that $\delta_i = \pi_{i2} - \pi_{i1} \implies \pi_{i2} = \delta_i + \pi_{i1}$. We can then rewrite the log-likelihood as

$$\begin{aligned} \ln L &= \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i1}}{\pi_{i1}} + \sum_i \ln \binom{n_{i2}}{\pi_{i2}} + \sum_i x_{i1} \ln \pi_{i1} \\ &+ \sum_i x_{i2} \ln(\delta_i + \pi_{i1}) + \sum_i (n_{i1} - x_{i1}) \ln(1 - \pi_{i1}) \\ &+ \sum_i (n_{i2} - x_{i2}) \ln(1 - \delta_i - \pi_{i1}) \end{aligned}$$

Let $\ln L_0$ and $\ln L_a$ be the maximum log-likelihoods under H_0 and H_a , respectively. Then, the LRT statistic for testing H_0 against H_a can be obtained as

$$LRT = 2[\ln L_a - \ln L_0] \sim \chi_{K-1}^2.$$

Binomial $C(\alpha)$ test

For the convenience of the derivation of the $C(\alpha)$ test statistic, we re-parameterize δ_i under H_a by $\delta_i = \delta + \alpha_i$, $i = 1, \dots, k-1$, with $\alpha_k = 0$. Then testing $H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = \delta$ reduces to testing $H_0 : \alpha_1 = \dots = \alpha_{k-1} = 0$.

Let $\alpha' = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_{k-1})$ and $\omega' = (\delta, \pi_{i1}, \pi_{i2}, \dots, \pi_{ik})$, with ω' being treated as nuisance parameter. Let's denote $U = \frac{\delta l}{\delta \alpha} | \alpha = 0$, $V = \frac{\delta l}{\delta \omega} | \alpha = 0$, $A = E(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha \delta \alpha'} | \alpha = 0)$, $C = E(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \alpha \delta \omega} | \alpha = 0)$, and $D = E(-\frac{\delta^2 l}{\delta \omega \delta \omega'} | \alpha = 0)$

The $C(\alpha)$ test (Neyman, 1959 and Saha, 2013) based on the residual $S(\omega) = U(\omega) - \beta' V(\omega)I$, for testing H_0 against H_a , is given by

$$\hat{S}(\hat{A} - \hat{C}\hat{D}^{-1}\hat{C}')^{-1}\hat{S}',$$

which asymptotically follows χ_{k-1}^2 as $n_{ij} \rightarrow \infty$.

5. Simulation Study for Test Procedures

Following Lui and Kelly (2000), we conducted the simulation study to check the performance in terms of the Type I error rate of the previous seven test methods, along with our two proposed likelihood-based test statistics, (i) Binomial LRT and (ii) Binomial $C(\alpha)$ test methods.

We follow the instructions of Lui and Kelly (2000) to generate random samples. As mentioned, the probability π_{i2} varies between centers due to center effects, we set $\pi_{i2} = .10 + .70p$, where p is generated from a beta distribution with mean $\pi = \alpha/(\alpha + \beta)$ and variance $\pi(1 - \pi)/(T + 1)$ with $T = \alpha + \beta$. We then set $\pi_{i1} = \pi_{i2} + \tau$, here τ is the underlying common risk difference. We have performed simulations for $\tau = 0.1$ and 0.2 . Note that p follows the beta distribution with $T=2$, and $\pi = 0.5$ is equivalent to assuming that p follows a uniform distribution on $(0,1)$. We generate the sample size n_{ij} following the probability mass function $f(n_{ij}) = 0.20$ for $n_{ij} = n - s$, where n is a given fixed constant and $s = 2, 1, 0, -1, -2$. We have taken the intraclass correlation

$\rho(= 1/[2(T + 1)])$ from approximately 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2; the number of centers K equals 8, 16, 20 and 30; and the mean treatment group size per center $E(n_{ij}) = n$ has been considered 4,8,10,15,20,25,30,40 and 60. All results are obtained using R codes. For each configuration of the above sets of parameters, we generated 10,000 repeated samples under the null hypothesis. We calculated Type I error rates for the nine test procedures, including seven previous and two new proposed methods. Results have been provided in Table 1.

From the results given in Table 1, it can be seen that the parametric test procedures, LRT and $C(\alpha)$, perform much better than the other non-parametric test procedures developed by Lipsitz et al. (1998) in terms of Type-I error rate.

6. Data Analysis

After simulation, we have provided the detailed analysis of two separate datasets. First one is the example when the null hypothesis is accepted, whereas, for the second one, the null hypothesis of testing the homogeneity of risk difference is rejected.

Example 1: Data from Multi-Center Randomized Clinical Trial

This data set contains information on the distribution of favorable responses to active drug and control treatment in a multi-center randomized clinical trial. This dataset contains information on the distribution of favorable responses to active drug and control treatment in a multi-center, randomized clinical trial. Data were collected from 8 clinics with 273 patients or 17 patients per clinic. Full data is available in Table 2.

We first need to test the following hypothesis:

$$H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_k = \delta$$

$$LRT = 8.583 \text{ with } p\text{-value} = 0.263$$

$$C(\alpha) = 13.065 \text{ with } p\text{-value} = 0.075$$

Conclusion: do not reject H_0 , indicating a non-significant between-clinic heterogeneity, that is, the two methods discussed under H_0 will be suitable to estimate the common risk difference. The details of estimation of the common risk difference using the weighted average method is given in Table 3.

Then, the common risk difference δ_{H_0} based on weighted average is

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_0} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i} = 0.124.$$

The details of estimation of the common risk difference using the weighted average (MH) method is given below in Table 4.

Then, the common risk difference δ_{H_0} based on MH method is

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_0}^* = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^* d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^*} = 0.128.$$

Example 2: Risk of stunting in left-behind children

Fellmeth et al. (2018) presented a meta-analysis investigating whether left-behind children and adolescents had different health conditions compared with children and adolescents with non-migrant parents. We focus on stunting as a binary outcome. This research identified 16 studies without zero events, including 38,779 children (17,066 left-behind children and adolescents and 21,713 children and adolescents with non-migrant parents). Because this dataset contains no zero events, we can use it to investigate whether each method gives a consistent estimate of RDs. Full dataset is available below in Table 5.

We first need to test the following hypothesis:

$$H_0 : \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \dots = \delta_K = \delta$$

$$LRT = 52.81 \text{ with } p\text{-value} = 0.0001$$

$$C(\alpha) = 55.21 \text{ with } p\text{-value} = 0.0001.$$

Conclusion: H_0 is rejected, indicating a significant between-study heterogeneity so the DL and HO methods under H_a will be suitable to estimate the overall risk difference. Details of DL method has been provided below in Table 6.

Estimating Risk Difference: DL Method

Based on Table 6, we obtain

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^K w_i (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0})^2 = 52.71.$$

The DL estimator of σ_u^2 is given by

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u,DL}^2 = [Q - (k - 1)] / \left[\sum_i w_i - \frac{\sum_i w_i^2}{\sum_i w_i} \right] = 0.001.$$

Then, the overall risk difference δ_{H_a} based on DL method can be obtained as

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{DL,i} d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{DL,i}} = 0.014.$$

Here $w_{DL,i} = 1 / (\hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{u,DL}^2)$.

Estimating Risk Difference: HO Method

The HO estimator of σ_u^2 is given by

$$\hat{\sigma}_{u,HO}^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k (d_i - \hat{\delta}_{H_0})^2}{k-1} - \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \hat{\sigma}_i^2 = 0.002.$$

Then, the overall risk difference δ_{H_a} based on HO method can be obtained as

$$\hat{\delta}_{H_a} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{HO,i} d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^k w_{HO,i}} = 0.005.$$

Here $w_{HO,i} = 1/(\hat{\sigma}_i^2 + \hat{\sigma}_{u,HO}^2)$.

7. Conclusion

Our primary objective in this research is extending our previous work on testing the homogeneity of risk difference across multiple centers. We would like to continue working on estimating the overall risk difference under H_0 and H_a respectively. Apart from the methods developed in the reference paper (Guo et al., 2022), we would like to suggest a number of alternative methods of estimating overall RD under both null and alternative hypotheses and compare their performances in terms of Bias and MSE.

8. References

- Beitler PJ and Landis JR. A Mixed-Effects Model for Categorical Data. *Biometrics*, Vol. 41, No. 4 (1985), pp. 991-1000.
- Chu et al. Bivariate Random Effects Models for Meta-Analysis of Comparative Studies with Binary Outcomes: Methods for the Absolute Risk Difference and Relative Risk. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*, 2010.
- DerSimonian R and Laird N. Meta-analysis in clinical trials. *Control Clin Trials* 1986; 7: 177–188.
- Fellmeth G, Rose-Clarke K, Zhao C, et al. Health impacts of parental migration on left-behind children and adolescents: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet* 2018; 392: 2567–2582.
- Guo J, Xiao M, Chu H and Lin L. Meta-analysis methods for risk difference: A comparison of different models. *Statistical Methods and Medical Research*, 2022.
- Hedges L and Olkin I. Statistical methods for meta-analysis. Orlando, FL: Academic Press, 1985.
- Hunter JE and Schmidt FL. Methods of meta-analysis: correcting error and bias in research findings. 3rd ed. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications, 2015.
- Paule RC and Mandel J. Consensus values and weighting factors. *J Res Natl Bur Stand (1934)* 1982; 87: 377–385.

Table 1: Type I error rate for the simulation 10000 replications: $\rho = 0.05, \tau = 0.1$.

K	n	LRT	$C(\alpha)$	Q_{WLS}	Z_{WLS}^2	Z_{LWLS}	$Z_{WLS,R}^2$	$Z_{WLS,R}^{*2}$	Z_V^2	Z_K^2
8	4	0.109	0.113	0.24	0.185	0.219	0.084	0.004	0.029	0.054
	8	0.099	0.084	0.138	0.095	0.113	0.102	0.008	0.086	0.093
	10	0.09	0.063	0.117	0.09	0.101	0.117	0.008	0.077	0.114
	15	0.071	0.068	0.091	0.059	0.059	0.114	0.006	0.107	0.112
	20	0.054	0.054	0.076	0.048	0.058	0.109	0.009	0.122	0.104
	25	0.061	0.066	0.079	0.044	0.044	0.127	0.015	0.118	0.123
	30	0.059	0.048	0.057	0.031	0.048	0.136	0.01	0.112	0.132
	40	0.055	0.052	0.054	0.03	0.059	0.12	0.014	0.109	0.117
60	0.044	0.057	0.05	0.03	0.05	0.108	0.005	0.12	0.108	
16	4	0.18	0.190	0.409	0.35	0.355	0.067	0.044	0.155	0.102
	8	0.112	0.082	0.165	0.135	0.139	0.099	0.075	0.113	0.113
	10	0.078	0.073	0.121	0.09	0.129	0.115	0.082	0.093	0.135
	15	0.078	0.059	0.098	0.077	0.075	0.115	0.082	0.094	0.127
	20	0.08	0.044	0.083	0.057	0.068	0.122	0.074	0.113	0.128
	25	0.067	0.05	0.069	0.048	0.066	0.124	0.076	0.117	0.129
	30	0.054	0.055	0.073	0.051	0.069	0.117	0.084	0.103	0.114
	40	0.066	0.054	0.061	0.042	0.067	0.117	0.081	0.117	0.124
60	0.067	0.052	0.07	0.045	0.052	0.129	0.099	0.143	0.134	
20	4	0.161	0.247	0.452	0.412	0.421	0.034	0.033	0.205	0.079
	8	0.098	0.093	0.186	0.152	0.178	0.083	0.061	0.103	0.109
	10	0.091	0.086	0.133	0.105	0.119	0.095	0.067	0.092	0.112
	15	0.084	0.073	0.113	0.096	0.088	0.11	0.079	0.087	0.126
	20	0.07	0.064	0.077	0.062	0.072	0.113	0.09	0.088	0.112
	25	0.061	0.061	0.068	0.05	0.067	0.106	0.074	0.107	0.107
	30	0.059	0.053	0.076	0.052	0.062	0.098	0.073	0.097	0.112
	40	0.061	0.048	0.062	0.051	0.047	0.106	0.088	0.108	0.101
60	0.066	0.039	0.07	0.048	0.047	0.112	0.087	0.112	0.122	
30	4	0.16	0.191	0.567	0.515	0.529	0.076	0.078	0.219	0.081
	8	0.13	0.091	0.048	0.201	0.226	0.05	0.04	0.062	0.094
	10	0.095	0.078	0.169	0.136	0.157	0.058	0.051	0.06	1.103
	15	0.077	0.069	0.116	0.095	0.106	0.077	0.066	0.065	0.092
	20	0.072	0.059	0.084	0.068	0.073	0.091	0.078	0.085	0.104
	25	0.056	0.061	0.081	0.062	0.076	0.078	0.066	0.066	0.091
	30	0.072	0.063	0.082	0.072	0.052	0.092	0.078	0.087	0.109
	40	0.064	0.048	0.072	0.053	0.056	0.108	0.087	0.083	0.113
60	0.055	0.051	0.073	0.058	0.059	0.100	0.080	0.091	0.100	

Table 2: Distribution of favorable response to active drug and control treatment from multicenter randomized clinical trial.

Clinic	Treatment	n_1	Y_1	Treatment	n_2	Y_2
1	Drug	36	11	Control	37	10
2	Drug	20	16	Control	32	22
3	Drug	19	14	Control	19	7
4	Drug	16	2	Control	17	1
5	Drug	17	6	Control	12	0
6	Drug	11	1	Control	10	0
7	Drug	5	1	Control	9	1
8	Drug	6	4	Control	7	6

Table 3: Weighted Average Method.

Clinic	$\hat{\sigma}_i^2$	w_i	$d_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$
1	0.0112	89.09	0.035
2	0.0147	67.96	0.112
3	0.0224	44.54	0.368
4	0.0100	99.08	0.066
5	0.0134	74.44	0.342
6	0.0075	133.10	0.080
7	0.0429	23.27	0.088
8	0.0545	18.34	-0.190

Table 4: MH Method.

Clinic	w_i^*	$d_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$
1	18.25	0.035
2	12.31	0.112
3	9.5	0.368
4	8.24	0.066
5	7.03	0.342
6	5.24	0.080
7	3.21	0.088
8	3.23	-0.190

Table 5: Dataset of risk stunting in left-behind children.

Study	e_1	n_1	e_2	n_2
Graham and Jordan (2013a)	22	237	54	243
Graham and Jordan (2013b)	41	255	42	227
Ban et al. (2017)	379	2426	609	3708
Feng et al. (2010)	496	1132	499	1095
Wang et al. (2011)	25	590	12	285
Mou et al. (2009)	1276	7585	1231	7557
Xie et al. (2013)	212	675	133	441
Chen et al. (2013)	224	1157	193	1157
Gao et al. (2010)	33	541	126	2245
Onyango et al. (1994)	33	69	33	85
Xia et al. (2011)	77	318	138	757
Pan and Chen (2014)	38	309	38	460
Yu et al. (2013)	31	200	204	1961
Chen et al. (2012)	54	362	12	148
Li et al. (2011)	44	738	18	789
Tao et al. (2016)	23	472	3	355

Table 6: DL Method.

Study	$d_i = \hat{\pi}_{i1} - \hat{\pi}_{i2}$	$w_i = 1/\hat{\sigma}_i^2$
1	-0.129	937.56
2	-0.024	837.93
3	-0.008	10946.40
4	-0.017	2252.30
5	0.0002	4755.28
6	0.005	27403.22
7	0.0124	1255.04
8	0.0267	3920.61
9	0.0094	7945.07
10	0.0900	155.99
11	0.0598	1292.01
12	0.0403	1946.31
13	0.0509	1423.67
14	0.0680	1170.91
15	0.03680	9594.60
16	0.04027	8209.37